

Comparative Analysis of Supervised Machine Learning Algorithms for COVID-19 Prediction

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Abstract

With the emergence of COVID-19 as an unprecedented pandemic, the health structure of both the developed and underdeveloped world not only seemed stranded but terrible. The human interface was faced with the dilemma of infection causing the health workers fall prey to the disease while identifying the presence of the disease among the patients. Given the nature of the disease, it is needed to mitigate the effects of spread by resorting to technological advancements for diagnosis of the disorder using machine learning algorithms. In this paper, three supervised machine learning algorithms; Decision Tree, Naïve Bayes, and Logistic Regression have been utilized for the prediction of the disease encompassing nine attributes considering various combinations of symptoms. A comparative analysis of the algorithms used revealed that Decision Trees with 99% accuracy and 98% precision, rendered it the most viable and accurate technique for the diagnosis of COVID-19 disease.

Index Terms: COVID-19, Disease Prediction, Machine Learning Algorithms, Pandemic, Prediction Models.

I. INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

The emergence of a local virus in Wuhan City, China in December 2019, capable of being transmitted from one individual to another, choked the entire globe from superpowers to the most underdeveloped countries, was declared the new global pandemic [1] coronavirus (COVID-19).

The novel coronavirus (COVID-19) has emerged as one of the most dangerous pandemics witnessed by the world in the last hundred years [2].

Initially presumed to be a local virus in China, gradually it paralyzed the entire world practically exposing the vulnerability of even the most advanced health systems worldwide making it amply clear that the world was not advanced enough in medical science to prevent such a pandemic. Resultantly the globe went to a grinding halt when the virus forced the world to resort to a virtual lockdown in 2020 [3].

COVID-19 proved to be a disaster with approximately 87958 people out of every 1 million being infected and 873 people in each million dead showing the danger of the disease [4]. With this magnitude of infection, the most modern and effective global healthcare systems like the UK, US, and European countries, seemed helpless. The testing capabilities of the countries were curtailed owing to the risk of getting the health workers being infected. The inability to facilitate numerous cases simultaneously necessitated the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) to

identify the disease without any fear of infection to the health care providers. The most typical signs of COVID-19-certified patients are characterized as fever, dry cough, myalgia (muscle pain), dyspnea (shortness of breath), conjunctivitis (pink eye), and headache. However, pain in the chest and paralysis may occur in a few extreme cases. Paradoxically in certain cases, patient infected with COVID does not even have any of the declared symptoms (asymptomatic) which further aggravated the already compound phenomenon [5], and [6].

Table I shows the general symptoms of COVID-19 disease.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) an evolving technology, has outright assisted to combat the novel coronavirus by expeditiously providing high-quality diagnosis outcomes and eased out the human resource involved in the diagnosis thus helping them utilize their services in providing curative services to the public [7-9]. Prediction models have been created to evaluate the risk of infection by combining several features [10].

Many disease prediction techniques based on supervised Machine Learning (ML) algorithms including J48 Decision Tree (J48 DT), Random Forest (RF), Support Vector Machine (SVM), K- Nearest Neighbors (k-NN), and Naive Bayes (NB), Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP), Logistic Regression (LR), and Artificial Neural Network (ANN) have been developed for diseases such as cardiovascular, dengue, diabetes, and others [11].

Our work focuses on comparing diverse ML algorithms including Naïve Bayes, Decision Tree, and Logistic Regression (supervised machine learning techniques) to identify the symptoms/causes and factors leading to the increased positivity of COVID-19 infected patients. Section II addresses the literature review. Section III explains the framework for detecting COVID-19 in the dataset. Section IV explains the experimental result of the techniques used followed by a conclusion in Section V.

Table I: Symptoms of COVID-19

Basic	Medium	Extreme
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fever, • Tiredness, and • Dry Cough. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conjunctivitis, • Chills, • Headache, • Severe Pains, • Diarrhea, • Aches Sore Throat, • Tastelessness, • Skin Rashes, • Toe and Fingers Discoloration. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dyspnea, • Pain in the Chest or, • Pressure, • Aponia or Paralysis.

II. RELATED WORK

The study performs an analysis of COVID-19 datasets to find out age brackets most affected by COVID-19 [12]. ML methods are employed to produce assorted prediction models and their working is calculated and measured. Other ML models such as SVM, KNN+NCA, Decision Tree Classifier, Gaussian Naive Bayesian (NB) Classifier, Multilinear Regression, Logistic Regression, and XG Boost Classifier showed less accurate results than the Random Decision Forest Regressor and Random Decision Forest Classifier. The findings revealed that people between the ages of 20 and 50 were at significant risk of catching COVID-19.

In another study, the authors formulated a ML model which was developed via training on observations from 51,831 people i.e., patients examined out of which 4769 were affirmed COVID-19 patients [10]. The data in the test set came up from the posterior week (47,401 examined people out of which 3624 were proven COVID-19 positive). The model produced COVID-19 test answers utilizing merely eight (8) binary attributes: gender, age 60, recognized contact with a tested positive person, and the comportment of five (5) early on clinical indications with great accuracy establishing the model useful for deployment globally for influential medium screening and testing in the broader population as a precedent priority.

Research was conducted that employs ML algorithms to predict serious COVID-19 cases, depending on their condition at the time of admission to the hospital [1]. To predict the patient's deterioration, three (3) distinct ML models were employed and compared to presently proposed features aside from the APACHE-II risk prediction score. There were 162 patients hospitalized with mild COVID-19 symptoms among the 6995 patients assessed, and 25 (15.4%) of them worsened to critical situations. The key outcome was the likelihood of developing critical illnesses like mechanical ventilation, multiple organ failure, ICU hospitalization, or demise. ML models surpassed additional parameters, such as the APACHE II score (ROC AUC of 0.92 vs. 0.79, respectively), predicting essential COVID-19 indications

with 88.0% recall, 92.7% precision, and 92.0% accuracy. The most crucial variables in the model were white blood cells, time from indications to admittance, oxygen (O₂) saturation, and blood lymphocyte number in the APACHE II score. Utilizing the COVID-19 indications and the present dataset, the author investigated multiple supervised ML algorithms to develop a model for examining and predicting COVID-19 [11]. On the WEKA tool, different algorithms such as J48 Decision Tree, Random Decision Forest, Support Vector Machine, K-Nearest Neighbors, and Naive Bayes were examined and compared to determine the accuracy of categorized samples, their mean absolute error and the time necessary to create the model. The Support Vector Machine with Pearson VII universal kernel beat former techniques with 98.81 percent accuracy and a mean absolute error of 0.012.

To categorize textual clinical reports into four categories, by machine learning techniques, the authors did feature engineering of Term Frequency/Inverse Document Frequency (TF/IDF), a Bag-Of-Words (BOW), and report length. When these characteristics were taken into consideration, logistic regression and Multinomial Naive Bayes surpassed other ML algorithms with 96.2 percent testing accuracy [13].

Given the widespread availability of rapid automated profiling of peripheral blood samples, another research was conducted on how data from COVID-19 affectees peripheral blood could be utilized to predict clinical results. They fused statistical comparisons and correlation methods with ML algorithms, to investigate clinical datasets from COVID-19 patients with recognized results. Their findings indicated various clinical quantifiable characteristics in blood samples that distinguished healthy people from COVID-19-infected patients and demonstrated predictive value for the severity of COVID-19 symptoms later in life [14].

A free mobile application launched in the United Kingdom gathered the data from an app-based symptom tracker. It collected the data from individuals and tracked it in real-time keeping track of COVID-19 progress. Running the logistic regression on data by adjusting age, gender, and Body Mass Index (BMI), researchers found out that only anosmia (smell loss), sense of taste, tiredness, continuous cough, and loss of appetency were the best symptoms for the symptom prediction model for COVID-19 [15].

Researchers used real-time data and applied CNN-based techniques to predict the number of COVID-19 confirmed, recuperated, and death instances. They used the prophet algorithm, an auto-regressive integrated model, and a long short-term memory neural network (LSTM) for prediction [16].

The authors in [17] applied ML classifiers like Linear Regression, Multi-Layer Perception (MLP), and Vector Auto Regression to forecast COVID-19 blowouts. The dataset was collected from Johns Hopkins University's COVID-19 data repository, concentrating on Asian countries' COVID-19 cases. In a recent research, various ML algorithms were compared for predicting COVID-19 mortality rate in hospitalized patients [18]. Data from 1500 eligible patients was extracted from the Ayatollah Taleghani Hospital registry. The top three predictors were dyspnea, ICU entry, and oxygen treatment. The study found

that Random Decision Forest (RDF) had much improved functioning than other ML algorithms, with accuracy, recall, precision, specificity, and ROC of 95.03%, 90.70%, 94.23%, 95.10%, and 99.02% respectively. ML-based predictive models could help identify patients at increased risk of fatality and inform appropriate treatments.

Moreover, [19] the researchers proposed a hybrid deep learning framework, the COVID-CheXNet system, to decrease load on radiologists and contain the spread of the pandemic. The system enhanced contrast and noise levels in chest X-ray images, fusing results from two pre-trained models. The system achieved accuracy of 99.99%, recall of 99.98%, precision of 100%, and F1-score of 99.99%. The COVID-19 patients accounted for 51,831 people in the study, with 4769 verified. The authors were able to diagnose COVID-19 with maximum accuracy using ML and trained the model while considering merely eight features for instance gender, age, exposure to positive patients, and five early clinical indications [10].

III. METHODOLOGY

The proposed methodology comprises steps from A to E. Step A explains how the data was collected. In step B data pre-processing is discussed. In step C, feature engineering is elaborated. Step D defines the basics of algorithms used in modeling. Step E explains the model evaluation. Figure I shows a visual representation of the methodology discussed.

Figure I: Proposed Methodology

A. Data Collection

The dataset that we have used in this study has been downloaded from the ‘Kaggle’ repository named “COVID-19 Symptoms Checker”. Based on some predefined standard symptoms, this data will aid in determining whether a person has coronavirus disease. These indications are established on the World Health

Organization (WHO), Ministry of Health and Family Welfare standards. The dataset comprises 27 features of fever, fatigue, trouble in respiration, dry coughing, sore throat, painfulness, non-symptom, nasal congestion, runny olfactory organ, diarrhea, non-experience, age (5 categories; 0-9 years, 10-19, 20-24, 25-59, 60+), gender (3 categories; male, female, transgender), severity (4 categories; none, mild, moderate, severe), contact (3 categories; yes, no, don’t know), and country. The spatial coverage of this dataset is for 10 countries i.e., China, Italy, Iran, the Republic of Korea, France, Spain, Germany, UAE, and others. On all these categorical features, a combination for every label in the feature is produced, rendering a combined total of 316800 choices [19], and [20].

B. Data Pre-Processing

The integral part of machine learning is to process the data before giving it to the algorithm because the quality of the data influences the learning ability of algorithms. In this step, we need to refine the data so that the algorithms perform well on the dataset. The steps that we have performed in pre-processing are dropping null values and removing duplicates.

C. Feature Extraction

Figure II visualizes the importance of features. Feature selection is the procedure of choosing a set of relevant features out of a bigger set, and it is crucial for building efficient and interpretable ML models. We have identified nine features relevant to symptoms by which the classification can be achieved. The identified features are dry cough, fever, difficulty in respiration, tiredness, sore throat, painful sensation, diarrhea, nasal congestion, and running nose. Four categories of severity (none, mild, moderate, and severe) are merged as one target feature. The Country feature is not considered a symptom of the disease so it is dropped. So out of 27 parameters in the dataset, 22 are considered to have an impact on the occurrence of disease. The significant features having a visible impact on disease occurrences are identified using the Random Forest Algorithm.

The Random Decision Forest algorithm is often used for feature selection due to its intrinsic ability to automatically identify how essential a feature is [21]. Random Decision Forest is an ensemble learning based model, that uses several decision trees (DTs) and merges their predictions. Non-linear relationships between features and the COVID-19 virus severity were well captured by the Random Forest Algorithm.

The Hyper-parameters used are described as follows:

number of estimators = 100,
 criterion = "Gini",
 maximum depth = None,
 minimum sample split = 2,
 minimum sample leaf = 1,
 maximum features = "auto",
 maximum leaf nodes = None,
 minimum impurity decrease = 0.0,
 bootstrap = True,
 oob score = False,
 random state = 42.

Figure II: Visualization of Selected Features

Figure III shows the percentage of occurrence count of the selected features using the Random Forest algorithm.

Figure III: Occurrence Count of Selected Features

D. Model Training

Three supervised machine learning algorithms were utilized for modeling, i.e. Logistic Regression, Decision Tree, and Naïve Bayes. The data was split in a 75:25 ratios, where 75% was used for training while 25% was later used for testing purposes.

1) Logistic Regression:

Based on the relationship between the numerical variable and the label, the Logistic Regression algorithm predicts the numerical variable's class. It receives the nine features that were chosen in feature engineering as input and estimates the probability of membership to a class. Posterior probabilities are determined using a binary class of severity features as described in eq. (1).

$$P(x) = \frac{e^{\varphi T \theta k}}{1 + \sum_{k=1}^2 e^{\varphi T \theta k}} \quad \forall k = 1, 2 \quad (1)$$

2) Decision Tree:

Decision Tree is an alternative approach for classification, it builds a decision tree to produce the categorization model [13]. It classifies the region at the bottom of the tree after continuously dividing it based on the inputs. The severity feature is divided into binary categories by the leaf nodes. When creating a decision tree, a critical function known as the splitting criterion must be considered.

To achieve optimal performance, the function dictates how data should be segregated. By dividing intrinsic information gain by the information gain to get the information gain ratio i.e., in eq. (2).

$$IGR (Ex, \alpha) = \frac{IG}{IV} \quad (2)$$

Where:

IG = Information Gain,

IV = Intrinsic Information.

GridSearchCV from the sklearn library is used to perform a search over the specified hyper-parameter grid, and the best hyper-parameters are obtained using the best params attribute. Finally, the model is trained using the best hyper-parameters, and its performance is evaluated. The hyper-parameters used were "criterion": ["gini", "entropy"] with max_depth: [15], [20], and [21].

3) Naïve Bayes:

Naïve Bayes is a probabilistic ML algorithm established on the Bayes Theorem. Bayes' Theorem is an elementary mathematical rule applied for computing conditional probabilities. Conditional probability evaluates the probability of an event happening provided that some other

event has (by assumption, presumption, assertion, or evidence) took place. The nine features that were chosen in feature engineering were supplied as input to the model. The method uses the Bayes theorem to determine the final class. The hyper-parameter used is estimator= Maximum Likelihood Estimator from pgmpy estimators' class (Probabilistic Graphical Models in Python).

E. Model Evaluation

Three supervised ML algorithms i.e., Decision Tree (DT), Naïve Bayes (NB), and Logistic Regression (LR) were utilized for disease prediction. The results have been flashed in Table II. Accuracy and Precision are the essential metrics for any machine learning algorithm. Accuracy is the measure of overall correct predictions while precision embarks on how many are truly predicted. It is evident from the achieved accuracy and precision scores that the decision tree outperformed the other algorithms. Probabilistic graphical models like Bayesian Networks explicitly represent probabilistic connections between variables while decision trees are deterministic models which make predictions by recursively splitting the data samples established on the values of input attributes. At every node of the tree, a choice is formed founded on a specific attribute and a threshold value. The process carries on till a stopping criteria is reached, e.g., an upper limit set as maximum allowed tree depth or a minimal number of observations in a leaf node.

Decision Tree outperformed the other techniques as it can work for both continuous and categorical features with the limited available training dataset. By simply adhering to the rules utilized throughout information gain ratio i.e., in eq. (2). The process from the root to the leaf, the ultimate prediction (i.e., the classification of an instance) made when applying the model to a previously unrepresented instance is simple to comprehend and visualize.

Additionally, a probabilistic graphical model library in Python (pgmpy) is used to further extract out most relevant symptoms of COVID-19. It utilizes Variable Elimination as an inference method to further reduce the number of symptoms that have an impact on disease prediction. Variable Elimination is a useful method for computing marginal probabilities in a graphical model. Extraneous variables are eliminated from the joint probability distribution in order to calculate the desired marginal probability.

Figure IV displays the sample query. It was inferred from various combinations that nasal congestion, diarrhea, and running nose are not the main symptoms that can be seen in all the patients.

```
query= symptom_inference.map_query(
variables=['Severity'],evidence={'Fever':1, 'Dry-Cough':1, 'Sore-Throat':1, 'Nasal-Congestion':1, 'Pains':1, 'Difficult-y-in-Breathing':1, 'Diarrhea':1, 'Runny-Nose':1, 'Tiredness':1. 'None_Symptom':0})
```

Figure IV: Query for Inference

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

For this work, we used a Windows PC with specifications of 8 GB of RAM and a 2.6 GHz processor. Machine learning categorization is performed using the Scikit learning tool in Python. To examine the adaptation of the model from training data to unlabeled data and to avoid overfitting, the original dataset is divided using cross-fold 10 layers, employing 10-fold stratified evaluation. 24 features in the dataset have been reduced to nine for disease prediction using the Random Forest algorithm. The variable Elimination method further elaborates that out of 9 features, six features have more influence on the prediction of COVID-19 which are fever, pain, fatigue, dry cough, difficulty in respiration, and sore throat. Table II compares all machine learning algorithms that were employed to complete the challenge. The results demonstrate that Decision Tree surpassed its competitor algorithms, with a precision of 99% and accuracy of 98%.

Table II: Summarization of Performance Measures by Various ML Classifiers

Algorithm	Accuracy	Precision
Decision Tree (DT)	0.98	0.99
Naïve Bayes (NB)	0.965	0.97
Logistic Regression (LR)	0.96	0.98

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The research reveals that the major symptoms of the disease are dry coughing, fever, sore throat, fatigue, and difficulty in respiration. The attribute importance is not only calculated for the classifier models but also with repressors for prediction. The results reveal that Decision Tree has exceeded the other models regarding accuracy and precision.

Though the application of ML algorithms is a great advancement in the health sector; it does come with certain limitations. The efficacy of our model is highly dependent on the given data. Since the COVID-19 pandemic spread is global, the breadth and diversity of the dataset may not be sufficient to capture all significant trends. Taking into account variables like public health initiatives, healthcare infrastructure and demographics, our model's performance may change for various populations.

Interpreting forecasts cautiously is necessary when extending them to different populations.

In the future, more machine learning techniques can be utilized for analyzing datasets of COVID-19 and its mutated variants.

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Authors Contributions

All the authors equally conducted and contributed to this study.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest and affirm that this is their original work. The information and data

gathered from all of the sources are appropriately acknowledged and cited in the reference section.

Data Availability Statement

The dataset is publicly available. Refer to [20] for the dataset URL.

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